

Rip Current Hazard Assessment in Tourist Beaches Of The Pameungpeuk Coastal, West Java, Indonesia

Ankiq Taofiqurohman¹
Andriano Sembiring¹

¹Department of Marine Science, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science.
Padjadjaran University

Corresponding author: ankiq@unpad.ac.id

Citation :

Taofiqurohman, A., & Sembiring, A. (2025). Rip Current Hazard Assessment in Tourist Beaches Of The Pameungpeuk Coastal, West Java, Indonesia. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14818102>

Abstract

Pameungpeuk Coastal is one of coastal tourism destinations in West Java Province, Indonesia. Pameungpeuk Coastal consists of four beach holiday destinations. Tourism management in Pameungpeuk Coastal is semi-professional and without professional lifeguards, hence the beaches are perilous especially because of rip current hazard. This study aim is to assess level of rip current hazard on the tourist beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal. Pameungpeuk Coastal boards Indian Ocean, thus beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal are considered exposed beach and are influenced by ocean swell wave, while tidal is a micro type. Beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal have an average wave height above 1.5 meters with the dominance of wave directions originating from the southwest. The rip current hazard value at beaches of Pameungpeuk Coastal are 2.5, this indicates that coastal hazard level in Pameungpeuk Coastal is moderate where rip current can appear all day.

Keywords : Rip current, Hazard, Pameungpeuk Coastal.

Introduction

Beach activities are dangerous and risky according to natural conditions, even though beach is tourists' favorite destination. The danger and risk of coastal tourism are physical, such as wave, rip current, and dangerous beach creatures. Several studies suggest that rip current is a major cause of casualties in coastal tourism activities (Brighton et al, 2013). Short and Hogan (1993) explain that rip currents and beach hazard levels are influenced by beach type and wave height. According to Gensini and Ashley (2010), rip current hazard is most likely to occur when high pressure on the surface creates an onshore wind. Scott et al (2014) stated that the main controlling factor of rip current hazards are beach type formation time span, sandbar morphology, wave height and tidal. In addition to wave height, wave direction also has a significant effect on rip current formation (Kumar and Prasad, 2013). Whereas according to Castelle et al (2016) rip current is divided into two types: Hydrodynamically-controlled and Boundary-controlled. These two types will become rip current hazard study materials by experts for future studies. Several studies have also examined rip current hazard prevention and rescue methods, for instance

Miloshis and Stephenson (2011), Dalrymple et al (2011), Drodzdzewski et al (2012), McCarroll et al (2015). These studies suggest swimmers to stay calm when they are caught by rip current, to swim parallel to the beach and never against the rip, then swim to the surface to breathe some air, and attract attention from people around the beach.

In Indonesia, most rip current researches are focused on beaches directly facing Indian Ocean such as Java Island southern coast (Kusmanto and Steyawan, 2013; Pangururan et al, 2015), Bali Island southern coast (Khoirunnisa et al,2013) and Rote Island coast (Radhitya and Harjoko, 2016), since wave in those beaches are generally high, consequently rip current is often formed. One of the tourist beaches with this criteria is Pameungpeuk Coastal, West Java Province, Indonesia. Pameungpeuk Coastal is located in southern part of West Java Province, which borders Indian Ocean (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of Pameungpeuk Coastal

The Pameungpeuk Coastal is a popular tourist attraction in West Java with almost 12 km of coastline. This area consists of four beaches are Karang Papak Beach, Santolo Beach, Cilauteureun Beach, and Sayang Heulang Beach. These beaches naming is based on literacy of the local community and each beach does not have a distinct boundary. Based on Taofiqurohman et al (2018) research, Pameungpeuk Coastal has five frequently visited areas: area A on Karang Papak Beach, area B on Santolo Beach, area C and D on Cilauteureun Beach, and area E on Sayang Heulang Beach (Figure 2). There is no underwater tourism potential in Pameungpeuk Coastal but it has beautiful coastal landscapes, as tourism attraction (Taofiqurohman et al, 2018). According to Backshall et al (2003), Pameungpeuk Coastal has beautiful and exquisite sandy beaches with strong currents.

Figure 2. Recreation areas around Pameungpeuk Coastal
(Source: Taofiqurohman et al, 2018)

One of coastal tourism development problems in Indonesia is tourist awareness lack regarding rip current hazard. In addition, quantity and quality of lifeguards are very deficient, especially in unexplored coastal areas. Lifeguards in Indonesia are usually local volunteers, consequently without expertise and operational equipment required by professional lifeguard standards. Tourism in Pameungpeuk Coastal is managed semi-professionally without lifeguards, so that in this way coastal hazards is highly possible. At the beginning of 2017, there were four accidents where rip current on Pameungpeuk Coastal beaches drag swimmers and the number of deaths stood at nine (Metrotvnews, 2017). Main cause of casualties in tourism activities in Pameungpeuk Coastal and Indonesia, in general, is lack of information about dangerous rip current in several areas. Therefore this study aims to assess the level of rip current hazard in tourists favorite bathing spots around Pameungpeuk Coastal. The result of the assessment is expected as a first step to prevent beach tourism accidents.

Materials And Methods

Bordering Indian Ocean, Pameungpeuk Coastal has naturally high waves with deep bathymetry. Bathymetric surveys at Pameungpeuk Coastal are high risk and dangerous, therefore the wave parameter data used is Wave watch 3 (WW 3) data, while bathymetry data uses the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) data. Several studies using WW3 in Indonesian seas have been conducted, among others are simulation of significant wave height climatology by Sofian and Wijanarto (2010), study of Madden-Julian-Oscillation impact on wave height by Hilmi et al (2018), and analysis of ocean wave

characteristic in Western Indonesian seas by Rachmayani et al (2018). In general, WW3 data is reliable as wave data in Indonesian seas.

Rip current hazard assessment uses Dynamics of Rips and Implications for Beach Safety (DRIBS) method developed by Plymouth University (the Royal National Lifeboat Institution, 2014). DRIBS method is a rip current hazard assessment method based on the value of rip current forming factors on a beach. These forming factors are beach type, sandbar, wave and tidal. The higher the rip current hazard score, the more dangerous the beach is (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Rip current hazard forming factors and rip current hazard scale (Source: modification from the Royal National Lifeboat Institution, 2014)

To determine the type of beach, a classification of Dimensionless Fall Velocity (Ω) and Relative Tide Range (RTR) is necessary, using following equations (Short, 1996):

$$\Omega = \frac{H_b}{W_s T}$$

$$RTR = TR/H_b$$

with

- Ω : Dimensionless Fall Velocity
- RTR : Relative Tide Range
- TR : Mean spring tide range (m)
- H_b : Breaker wave height (m)
- W_s : Sediment fall velocity (m/sec)
- T : Wave period (sec)

Breaking wave height (H_b) is obtained from graph of breaking wave height (Goda, 1970 in Franco, 2016). The RTR and Ω scores determine the type of beach as follows

Results

Among five recreation spots, only three of them are safe for swimmers: Karang Papak Beach, Santolo Beach and Sayang Heulang Beach. Cilauteureun Beach areas are rocky, therefore they are considerably dangerous. Based on field observations result, Pameungpeuk Coastal was dominated by white sand. According to Setiady (2012), white sand in Pameungpeuk Coastal is categorized as fine sand. Based on Short (1996), fine sand is 3 ϕ (phi) grain size fraction with a falling speed of 0.024 m/sec. WW3 data processing result shows dominance of wave direction coming from southwest, with wave height in the deep sea of 1.99 meters while average period is 14 seconds. Every month on Java southern coast, the wave height can reach up to 2 meters dominantly from southwest, as an effect of southwest monsoon in Indian Ocean (Chen et al, 2015; Kurniawan and

Khotimah, 2015). To calculate the breaking wave height in the surf zone a depth of 10 meters is used, at where the wave starts to become unstable. Based on the breaker wave height, sediment fall velocity and wave period of the beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal, the dimensionless fall velocity (Ω) was obtained as follows (Table 6):

Table 6. The dimensionless fall velocity (Ω) scores

Beach	Slope	H _b	W _s	T _p	Ω
Karang Papak	0.013	2.59	0.024	14	7.72
Santolo	0.01	2.55	0.024	14	7.59
Sayang Heulang	0.032	2.9	0.024	14	8.66

From the value of dimensionless fall velocity (Ω) and RTR, beach types are found in Pameungpeuk Coastal (Table 7).

Table 7. The beach type in Pameungpeuk Coastal

Beach	Ω	RTR	Type
Karang Papak	7.72	0.62	Dissipative
Santolo	7.59	0.63	Dissipative
Sayang Heulang	8.66	0.55	Dissipative

Karang Papak Beach, Santolo Beach and Sayang Heulang Beach are dissipative beach type which average wave height can reach more than 1.5 meters. Like the beaches in South Java, facing Indian Ocean directly, Pameungpeuk Coastal is included in exposed coasts and is influenced by ocean swell wave. Pameungpeuk Coastal tide type is a semidiurnal mixed tide prevailing with a tidal range of 1.6 meters, included in micro tidal tide type. Based on beach type, wave and tidal parameters, rip current hazard score at Karang Papak Beach, Santolo Beach and Sayang Heulang Beach is 2.5, this indicates hazard level moderacy of rip current (Figure 5). Tidal ranges below 2 m signify that rip current can occur all day.

Figure 5. The rip current hazard forming scores in Pameungpeuk Coastal beaches

Discussion

The American Meteorological Agency, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) stated that rip current moderate hazard levels indicate rip current forming potential is higher so that only competent swimmers are allowed to enter the water (NWS, 2013). Based on the beach position and hazard status, there are three recreational zones in Pameungpeuk Coastal. The zone 1 includes Karang Papak and Santolo Beach, zone 2 is Cilauteureun Beach and zone 3 is Sayang Heulang Beach (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Map of recreational zones status in Pameungpeuk Coastal beaches

In fact, tourists who bathe in Pameungpeuk Coastal are mostly not competent and experienced swimmers, so that rip current dragging occurs quite often. Therefore, a lifeguard in Pameungpeuk Coastal is definitely necessary, especially during holiday such as New Year's eve. During peak season, visitors in Pameungpeuk Coastal are more than three times than usual (Figure 7). In addition to rip current, on a dissipative beach, other hazardous causes are high waves and wide surf zones (Short and Hogan, 1993).

Figure 7. Left: Pameungpeuk Coastal during weekday (Source: personal collection), right: holiday season (Source: Yusup, 2016)

Rip current is a natural phenomenon, so risk minimalization is essential. The easiest way is to put up warning signs and notice boards about restricted areas and unsafe times to swim. Warning signs and notice boards are important in order to make tourists learn more about danger level of places they plan to visit. In UK, safe beach is marked by red and yellow flags, as recommended by International Life Saving Federation (ILSF), with lifeguard patrols standing by (Woodward et al, 2015). Professional lifeguard with adequate equipment in tourism area is highly necessary to prevent drowning (Yang et al, 2014).

Another preventing action is public education about rip current phenomena and survival tips. Indonesian government and people can adopt the efforts made by several countries to reduce casualties due to rip current hazard. In America, there is Rip Current Awareness Week program every summer. This program encourages beach safety practitioners to use visual displays and research approaches to share information and experiences from rip current survivors (Brander et al, 2011). Brazil has developed Beach Management and Safety Project which can reduce accidents up to 80% (Klein et al, 2003).

In Indonesia, beach safety education, especially beach tourism is very rarely performed; therefore a joint effort is needed between community, government and entrepreneurs in campaigning safe beach tourism. Beach danger prevention is ideally started from pre-elementary and elementary school using a story or game approach. In secondary schools, knowledge of beach hazards is improved to swimming and water safety skills and basic water rescue techniques. Beach hazard information and its prevention are visualized through pamphlets, posters, warning boards or loudspeakers. Information about coastal hazards must include dangerous areas and times for bathing or swimming, number of incidents and casualties, weather and tidal information. During holiday season, beach tourism management should increase number of lifeguards and alert supporting agencies such as police, firefighters, coast guard and hospitals.

Conclusion

Rip current is a natural phenomenon that often occurs in Pameungpeuk Coastal. Under certain conditions, rip current causes fatalities, especially tourists who bathe in Pameungpeuk Coastal beaches. Beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal have an average wave height above 1.5 meters with dominance of wave directions originating from the southwest, where the beaches face Indian Ocean directly. Calculation results showed that breaking wave height for each beach was relatively equal, i.e. between 2.55 and 2.9 meters with a wave period of 14 seconds. The Dimensionless Fall Velocity value at Pameungpeuk Coastal is between 7.59 and 8.66 while the Relative Tide Range (RTR) value is between 0.55 and 0.62. Based on the Dimensionless Fall Velocity and Relative Tide Range (RTR), the beaches in Pameungpeuk Coastal are considered dissipative coast with medium rip current hazard rates.

According to analysis, the rip current hazard value at Karang Papak Beach, Santolo Beach and Sayang Heulang Beach is 2.5; this indicates moderate coastal hazard level. Having no professional lifeguard at Pameungpeuk Coastal, the first step to reducing the risk of rip current hazard is putting up warning signs and information boards about dangers of coastal tourism. In addition, a joint campaign is needed between community, government and business people.

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